

Synthesis of 4-Aminomethylxanthenes with Possible Central Nervous Stimulating Activity

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D. L. Re and co-workers¹ have shown that 7-hydroxychromones and related compounds undergo facile Mannich reaction when condensed with formaldehyde and a secondary base in ethanol, yielding the 8-aminomethyl derivatives. The position taken by the entrant group has been fixed on the basis of the earlier work of Rangaswami and Seshadri² and independent experimental proof. These aminomethyl derivatives have been found to act as powerful central nervous stimulants.

It is well known that introduction of an alkylamino group to the xanthone nucleus gives rise to compounds with pronounced physiological activity. Thus the Miracils A, B, and C (the various 1-dialkylaminoalkylaminoxanthenes), discovered by Mauss and co-workers³, and 2- and 3-dialkylaminoxanthenes, prepared by Mann and Turnbull⁴, are of great value in the treatment of Schistosomiasis. Hence it was felt desirable to attempt the synthesis of aminomethylxanthenes having an aminomethyl group directly linked to the xanthone nucleus instead of a substituted amino group, expecting them to exhibit central nervous stimulating activity.

In course of synthesis of xanthenes^{5,6} in these laboratories, 3-hydroxyxanthone has been found to resemble the 7-hydroxychromone in their chemical behaviour, such as formylation, Friedel-Crafts' rearrangement, etc. Hence as a typical example, 3-hydroxyxanthone has been submitted to the Mannich reaction employing formaldehyde and a secondary base like dimethylamine, piperidine, morpholine, etc., yielding the corresponding Mannich bases or their hydrochlorides. That the aminomethyl group has entered 4-position has been established by its subsequent conversion to the known formyl derivative⁵ by heating with hexamine and glacial acetic acid. The work is being extended to various 3-hydroxyxanthenes carrying alkyl, alkoxy, halogen, and other substituents in different positions of the xanthone molecule. These compounds will be submitted to pharmacological tests in due course. A more detailed paper will follow soon.

Mannich Reaction.—To a well-stirred mixture of the secondary amine (0.01*M*) and formaldehyde (1 ml), kept below 10°, was added dropwise a cold solution of 3-hydroxy-

1. *Nature*, 1959, 184, 362; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 1097.

2. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9A, 1, 7.

3. *Chem. Ber.*, 1948, 81, 19.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 747.

5. Puranik and Rajagopal, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, 96, 976.

6. *Idem*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 1089.

xanthone (0.01M) in ethanol (75 ml). The mixture was stirred for 1 hr. more and then refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. After removal of the solvent and the volatile products, the Mannich base was isolated as such or as its hydrochloride. Table I summarises the physical constants and analytical data of the 4-aminomethyl 3-hydroxyxanthenes, thus prepared.

TABLE I

Xanthone.	Appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
3-Hydroxy-4-dimethylamino.	Colorless cubes (ethanol)	165°	$C_{16}H_{15}O_3N$	4.82	5.20
Hydrochloride	Colorless rhombic prisms(ethanol-ether)	241-42°	$C_{16}H_{16}O_3NCl$	4.62	4.68
3-Hydroxy-4-piperidinomethyl.	Colorless cubes (ethanol)	152-53°	$C_{19}H_{19}O_3N$	4.21	4.53
Hydrochloride	Colorless needles (ethanol-ether)	242-43°	$C_{19}H_{20}O_3NCl$	4.08	4.05
3-Hydroxy-4-morpholinomethyl.	Colorless cubes (ethanol)	200-201°	$C_{18}H_{17}O_4N$	4.12	4.50
Hydrochloride	Rectangular plates (ethanol-ether)	236-37°	$C_{18}H_{18}O_4NCl$	3.78	4.03

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